

Software Architecture of the MOLAR-HRRT Reconstruction Engine

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Abstract— The *Motion-compensation OSEM List-mode Algorithm for Resolution-recovery Reconstruction (MOLAR)* is a complete system for managing and performing iterative PET reconstructions. Although it was designed for use with the ECAT HRRT, its pluggable component architecture is readily extendable to any PET scanner, list-mode or frame-mode. List-mode data are stored on a distributed set of linked lists of *event packets*. Each event packet stores all information needed for one coincidence event. The resolution model uses a distance-based approximation and assumes separability of the radial and axial factors. Since the complete computation of the global sensitivity image Q (the denominator outside the sum in the OSEM update equation) requires a back-projection of all 4.5×10^9 possible LORs in the HRRT at all time increments in the scan frame and is thus intractable, we have devised an approximation in which the back-projection is performed on only a randomized sub-sampling of LOR space. To test the randomized approach we generated 10 realizations of the Q image at various count levels and measured the average coefficient of variation (COV) per slice at each count level. We characterize the dependence of image noise on error in Q . We also provide a result demonstrating that we have achieved image resolution of less than 3 mm, a critical design goal.

I. INTRODUCTION AND GOALS

THE Motion-compensation OSEM List-mode Algorithm for Resolution-recovery Reconstruction (MOLAR) system is the result of an ongoing collaboration between three organizations in the NIH Intramural Research Program and CPS Innovations, Knoxville, TN, USA. It is a complete system for managing and performing high-resolution, iterative reconstructions [1]. MOLAR has been designed for use with the ECAT HRRT (High Resolution Research Tomograph [2], CPS Innovations) operating in list-mode. Due to the pluggable

component design of the software, however, the MOLAR reconstruction engine is readily adaptable to any PET scanner, including frame-mode scanners. Reconstructions are performed on a parallel cluster of commodity computers.

One of the goals of the project is to provide complete reference implementations (i.e., with physical effects incorporated into the model) of common iterative reconstruction algorithms such as OSEM [3] and BSREM [4]. Another goal of the project is to provide to the PET research community a general software framework for performing list-mode or frame-mode reconstructions on the HRRT or any other PET scanner. The framework has been designed to allow collaborating groups or individuals the opportunity to contribute their own components. We intend to release the software to the community and invite such collaborations.

II. FEATURES OF THE ENGINE

In the course of developing MOLAR, we carefully considered many design approaches. We believe that certain features are novel and deserve special mention. In the description of the features, we introduce (in italics) the names of a number of application programming interface (API) classes and functions. Section III puts these API elements in the proper context.

A. Event List

The list-mode data are stored in a distributed manner across the processors in a set of singly linked lists for forward-only traversal, with one list corresponding to the portion of one subset assigned to that processor. Each list element is an instance of the API *EventPacket* class which stores all the data needed by MOLAR to process that event, including the attenuation correction coefficient, randoms estimate, scatter estimate, number of events (to support frame-mode acquisition), crystal indices, motion-corrected event coordinates, and region-of-support bounds (to facilitate rapid forward- and back- projection). An *EventList* class, which manages the event list, can perform intelligent swapping of the list as needed to the compute-node's swap space when the list does not fit in the available memory. Events having LORs that do not intersect with the attenuating region of the object are flagged as such; they are used by the scatter correction module (for scaling) but not the reconstruction algorithm. Figure 1

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provides an illustration of how the events are distributed prior to storage in the event list.

B. Polaris Motion Correction

Patient motion is tracked via the Polaris Optical Tracking System (Northern Digital Inc., Waterloo, Ontario, Canada), an infrared system with an accuracy of 0.35-mm RMS. The raw

Fig. 1: Illustration of the process of event packet assembly and distribution. The API class name “House” is a play on a casino analogy in which the “dealer” obtains the event from the House and then distributes it to the appropriate “player”, i.e., processor.

Polaris data are converted into transformation matrices, time-stamped with respect to a common reference time, and stored in a separate file from the list-mode data. The time-stamps in the motion data file allow for synchronization with corresponding event data in the list-mode file. The generic concept of motion correction is supported by the abstract *MotionCorrection* API parent superclass, which is concretely subclassed by the *PolarisMotionCorrection* class.

C. Resolution Model

The system matrix includes a factor to represent the system geometry and resolution model, which is traditionally denoted $C_{i,j}$. The large number K of potential LORs on the HRRT ($K=4.5 \times 10^9$), coupled with the need to support motion correction (and hence arbitrary LOR positions) necessitated a scheme in which “chords” are computed on the fly during the reconstruction. To account for the effect of motion correction, the LOR index i needs to be a function of detector LOR k as well as time t . The resolution of each “chord” ($C_{i(k,t),j}, \forall j$) is assumed to be the product of two separable functions, in the radial and axial directions, respectively. These separable functions are then indexed by the distances Δr and Δz from the center of voxel j to the nearest position along the center of the LOR i , or $C_{i(k,t),j} = f_k^r(\Delta r_{i(k,t),j}) f_k^z(\Delta z_{i(k,t),j})$. The functions f^r and f^z are stored in memory from pre-computed resolution kernels for a table of fixed FWHM values. We have implemented Gaussian kernels in which the table is sampled for every 0.1-mm increment of FWHM; other implementations are under investigation and supportable by the framework as defined by the API class *ResolutionFunction*. For example, the framework supports asymmetric and non-Gaussian resolution models. The kernels are super-sampled as configured by the

user; we recommend a 10:1 super-sampling of voxel space. The distances $\Delta r_{i(k,t),j}$ and $\Delta z_{i(k,t),j}$ are computed on-the-fly during the forward-and-back projection operations in a computationally efficient manner. Care has been taken to ensure that the overall cost of this approach is no more than that of using pre-computed chords.

D. Randomized Global Sensitivity Image (Q)

The leading denominator of the OSEM update equation is the global sensitivity image Q , the back-projection of unity. The correct computation of Q , to include the effect of motion, would require a back-projection of all 4.5G-LORs at all times in the scan frame, i.e., for one subset,

$$Q_j = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \sum_{k=1}^K C_{i(k,t),j} A_{i(k,t)} N_k \Omega_{i(k,t),j} L_{k,t} dt$$

where T is the scan duration, K is the total number of possible LORs, $A_{i(k,t)}$ is attenuation, N_k is normalization, $\Omega_{i(k,t),j}$ is solid angle correction, and $L_{k,t}$ is the product of livetime, decay, and positron fraction. Since such a calculation is intractable, we approximate Q by randomly sampling LOR space. For the purpose of computing Q , a special randomized event list is generated to reflect the scan duration (and the subject motion in that duration), subject to a user-controllable parameter N_Q , the number of desired events in the randomized event list. The approximation is then (for any subset m out of M subsets),

$$Q_j^m \approx \frac{K}{N_Q M} \sum_{n_i=1}^{N_i} \sum_{k'=1}^{N_Q/N_i} C_{i(k',n_i),j} A_{i(k',n_i)} N_{k'} \Omega_{i(k',n_i),j} L_{k',n_i},$$

where k' is the randomly chosen LOR, N_i is the number of time units of the acquisition and n_i is the time unit index.

E. Simulation with Motion

The randomized event list concept is also applied to the simulation of acquisitions on the HRRT. The user provides as input the number of randomized events N_Q , the number of simulation realizations N_R , a “truth” emission distribution λ (which is assumed to be $E\{\mathbf{x}\}$ where \mathbf{x} is the underlying Poisson random vector), and a dummy list-mode data file which is used only for its time stamps and singles information. The time stamps are used to match the motion data. The reconstruction engine performs an event-by-event forward

projection using the same software components used in the reconstruction. It also calculates estimates of the random ($\hat{R}_{k'}$) and scatter ($\hat{S}_{i(k',t)}$) terms in the expected value:

$$\hat{y}_{i(k',t)} = T \left(\sum_j C_{i(k',t),j} A_{i(k',t)} N_{k'} \Omega_{i(k',t)} \lambda_j + \hat{R}_{k'} + \hat{S}_{i(k',t)} \right)$$

Poisson sampling is then performed on the expected value for each of the N_R realizations, i.e.

$$y_{i(k',t)}^r = \text{Poisson} \{ \hat{y}_{i(k',t)} \}, \quad r = 1, \dots, N_R.$$

Thus, this is not a true Monte-Carlo simulation but rather a technique to produce random realizations in a manner consistent with the physics model shown above. For most of the forward-projected events, it will be the case that $y_{i(k',t)}^r = 0$. For those cases where $y_{i(k',t)}^r \geq 1$, the event-realization is saved to a transmission buffer bound for the processor that is designated to save realization r . The simulation is implemented in class *Simulation*, a subclass of API parent abstract class *Algorithm*. The projection machinery in the parent class is thus used by the subclass.

F. Computational Features

Parallel computing: We have constructed a dedicated, commodity cluster to host the reconstruction engine. This cluster currently consists of 46 compute nodes from Penguin Computing, San Francisco, CA including 24 Altus 130 nodes (dual AMD Athlon1500 MHz processors, 2GB memory) and 22 Relion 130 nodes (dual Intel Xeon 2.8 GHz processors, 2 GB memory); a Procurve 4108gl gigabit switch (Hewlett Packard, Palo Alto, CA); and 7 TB of ACNA JetStor RAID storage (Advanced Computer and Network Corporation, Pittsburgh, PA). Although our worked has focused on commodity clusters, the compute-jobs can run on any system supporting the Message Passing Interface (MPI) standard.

Performance: Reconstruction time is roughly linear with number of counts and is roughly inversely linear with clock speed. A 50M-event iteration requires approximately 15 minutes on 20 of the dual Athlon 1500-MHz nodes or 12 of the dual Xeon 2.8 GHz nodes. Each subset-update requires a summation of the entire image (typically $256 \times 256 \times 207$ floating-point numbers) across all processors. This operation costs approximately 10 seconds on the gigabit fabric and grows slightly as the number of processors increases.

Event list swapping: When the event list becomes too large for storage in distributed memory, event list swapping is managed by the reconstruction application, as opposed to the operating system kernel. Consequently, the performance hit of managed event swapping is modest; when the event list is large enough to enable swapping, the cost of an iteration is no greater than 10% more than the hypothetical cost of the same iteration if sufficient memory were available to store the entire event list.

Good load balance is achieved by distributing events according to clock speed of the respective processors.

Image array indexing: the indexing order has a significant effect on performance. We found that best results are obtained when the axial index z is the middle index of the inner projection loop, where movement is primarily along the transaxial directions x or y .

Fig. 2: Software architecture diagram. Unified Modeling Language (WWW, www.uml.org) conventions apply. Only the most significant API functions are listed.

III. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 2 presents a schematic depicting the software architecture of the Molar engine. We have adopted an open-source, standards-based approach to the development of software. A wide array of freely downloadable software technologies have been incorporated into the development, configuration, testing, and release of the project's software.

The web application was developed in Java with the Struts model-view-controller framework and JDBC™ for performing queries on a MySQL database. The web application allows the user to manage datasets, choose parameters, and submit and monitor multi-frame reconstructions to the cluster. It provides

a set of input parameters as an XML file to the engine; otherwise the web application is decoupled from the cluster software. Jobs are controlled by the OpenPBS batch system (www.openpbs.org). Inter-processor communication is facilitated via LAM MPI (www.lam-mpi.org).

The numerical reconstruction software on the parallel cluster has been developed in C++. Contributing collaborators may provide their own implementations of the *House* that models the scanner and builds the event packets. Our software uses a component-based model for normalization and randoms [5,6]. We are testing an implementation of Watson's single-scatter simulation [7]; other implementations of the *Scatter* abstract superclass are possible and invited. Any algorithm implementation that is capable of operating on data from the *EventList* class can be supplied as a subclass of the *Algorithm* abstract class. As an extreme example, the class *Simulation* is a subclass of *Algorithm*.

IV. TESTS AND RESULTS

We have conducted a number of validation tests on many of the critical functional aspects of the reconstruction engine, including Polaris motion correction, resolution recovery, the appearance of Q , and the effect of noise in Q on image noise. Fig. 3 presents one of the motion correction tests in which a line source was inserted into a styrofoam phantom and rotated to 5 different positions roughly in the x-y plane during the frame duration. Reconstructions were performed with the motion correction option enabled as well as disabled. The corrected reconstruction is noteworthy considering the extensive amount of motion involved.

Fig. 3: Reconstruction of line source, rotated to 5 different positions during frame interval. Shown are z-projections without (L) and with (R) motion correction included in the reconstruction.

We have also tested the effect of noise in Q on noise in the image estimate λ . In this test, a uniform cylinder was scanned for durations 0.5-, 1-, 2-, and 4-min. (corresponding to 17M-, 33M-, 66M-, and 129M-events). The data from each of the scan durations were reconstructed several times, with each reconstruction corresponding to a particular randomized count level N_Q (10M, 20M, 40M, 80M, and 100M) as well as a particular scan duration. Non-uniformity in λ was assessed by measuring the COV in 22 regions of interest (ROIs) over 100 slices of a single reconstruction. These data were then

matched to corresponding data from the back-projections reported in Figs. 5 and 6. The average COVs of Q from these back-projections were taken over the same 100 slices for which the 22 ROIs were defined. The COV-of- Q data were then interpolated to the same N_Q values as were used to assess the non-uniformity of λ . Fig. 7 shows that noise in Q can have a significant impact on noise in the reconstructed image. Thus a high value of N_Q will be required to reduce $\text{COV}(Q)$ and lessen the impact of image noise.

Fig. 4: Reconstruction of Micro Deluxe phantom; average of 20 zoomed transaxial slices. (L) – after 2 OSEM iterations, 10 subsets, (R) – after 4 iterations, 10 subsets.

In order to assess our goal of achieving sub-3-mm resolution, we have reconstructed a 150M-event scan of the Micro Deluxe phantom (Data Spectrum Inc., Hillsborough, NC). The rod diameters of this phantom are 4.8-, 4.0-, 3.2-, 2.4-, 1.6-, and 1.2-mm with rod separation equal to twice the diameter. The result in Fig. 4 shows that the 3.2-mm rods are clearly resolved and that the 2.4-mm rods are largely resolved. The reconstruction for this test was performed using an isotropic Gaussian resolution model in which the FWHM is influenced by a variety of crystal-position factors.

Fig. 5: Sagittal (L) and transverse (R, contrast enhanced to show pattern) central slices of 104M-event Q image.

A previously untested aspect of our approach is the use of a randomization strategy to estimate Q . We have assessed the statistical quality of the randomized Q by back-projecting 10 realizations each of 5 different randomized count levels N_Q , namely 5M, 20M, 50M, 100M, and 200M. Fig. 5 provides cross-sectional views of the coefficient-of-variation (COV) image from the 100M-event realizations. The average COV value was calculated from a large region of interest in the 1st, 53rd, and 104th transaxial slices (out of 207 total slices), as presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Noise in the Q image versus number of randomized events in the backprojection.

Fig. 7: Nonuniformity in a uniform cylinder reconstruction versus number of randomized events. The OSEM reconstructions were taken to 1 iteration with 10 subsets.

V. DISCUSSION

The spoke and wheel patterns in the transaxial slice of Q are produced by gap “cancellation” along the LORs connecting gaps. These patterns illustrate the need to compute Q rather than estimate it with a smooth function. In the presence of subject motion, Q will be blurred in a motion-specific fashion. The COV results in Fig. 6 suggest that 100M-events will certainly be sufficient to produce a Q image with $\text{COV} < 1\%$ in most slices. However, the question remains as to whether a 1% COV in Q will yield sufficiently noise-free images.

Qi and Huesman [8] have reported that error in Q is approximately amplified in λ by the inverse of the Fisher information matrix. We have found that, after 1 OSEM iterations with 20 subsets, a decrease by 10% in a particular voxel Q_j results in an 800% increase in the corresponding

image voxel λ_j . This finding is roughly in agreement with Qi and Huesman. We are currently investigating the effect of smoothing Q , which reduces the error in λ but which may introduce bias.

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VII. REFERENCES

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